

Atlas of Variant Effects 2030 Roadmap: resolving human variants of uncertain significance

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Two decades after the International Human Genome Project revealed the first human genome sequence, and with millions of humans having since been sequenced, we remain largely unable to interpret the simplest (single-nucleotide) changes, even in the genome's best-understood, protein-coding regions harboring the vast majority of known disease-causing variation. This uninterpretable majority ends up classified as Variants of Uncertain Significance (VUS), which cannot be used to diagnose or treat disease, thus limiting the impact of genomic medicine.

Recent advances in experimental and computational technologies now enable determination of single nucleotide variant effects at scale. Applying these technologies comprehensively would generate an atlas of variant effects, with profound implications for understanding human biology and genomic medicine. Having largely overcome the challenges of sequencing human genomes and identifying the functional elements therein, we are now in a "third phase" of the genomics revolution focused on understanding, predicting and controlling genome function. Success in this functional phase of genomics will require that we comprehensively evaluate the impact of human variants on functional elements, phenotype and disease risk to understand how genetic variants alter molecular, cellular and organismal phenotypes. Community engagement in our vision of building an atlas of human variant effects is already broad and energetic, e.g., via the NHGRI's [Impact of Genomic Variation on Function](#) consortium (IGVF, over 500 members) and the international [Atlas of Variant Effects \(AVE\) Alliance](#) (over 700 members from over 50 countries).

At the [Clinical Atlas of Variant Effects meeting](#) (CLAVE meeting, July 2024, Pittsburgh USA), we developed recommendations for a draft atlas that can be realized by 2030, with a focus on empowering genomic medicine by resolving VUS. The draft atlas will be a compendium of experimentally determined variant effects from a variety of types of assays alongside model-based predictions. Variant effect data and predictions can, when validated and combined, provide the scale and biological insight needed to understand nearly all single nucleotide variants. To the extent that experimental and predictive data offer independent evidence when classifying patient-derived variants, both high-quality experimental measurements and predictions of every variant's effect are needed to resolve VUS. By discussing the advantages and disadvantages of investing resources in different ways, we developed a vision for a draft atlas that can be delivered by 2030. This document crystallizes infrastructure, technology development, data production and clinical translation efforts that CLAVE meeting attendees concluded are needed to produce a maximally useful draft 2030 atlas. Rough resource estimates are attached to each activity below and also in **Table 1** at the end of the document. The document contains draft appendices that offer detail on aspects of the roadmap.

Twin goals for a draft atlas in 2030: resolving VUS and modeling variant pathomechanism

Our vision for the draft 2030 atlas is that it be developed in service of two complementary but distinct goals. The primary goal is to empower genomic medicine by resolving VUS. Given this goal, most effort and available resources over the next five years should be applied toward executing and scaling existing assays and refining

predictive algorithms to evaluate all possible single nucleotide variant effects in clinically-relevant genes. A complete atlas would encompass all ~4,500 genes with moderate or stronger evidence of association with disease as cataloged by the Gene Curation Coalition. Among these genes, ~900,000 VUS, of which ~800,000 are missense, have been reported in ClinVar (Jan 1st, 2025), and the VUS are not distributed equally over genes mostly due to testing volume (**Figure 1a**). A realizable goal for a draft 2030 atlas is to generate data for reinterpreting ~70% of VUS which would encompass ~1,000 genes and attendant regulatory elements, selected based on VUS density, clinical need and assayability (**Fig 1b**). Over the past decade, variant effect data have been generated for ~50 human clinically relevant genes, so this goal represents an ~20-fold increase. Experiments and predictions would be developed to achieve the greatest scale possible while accurately discriminating between known benign and pathogenic variants. Driving VUS resolution *en masse* using this data would additionally require that the experimental and predictive data be calibrated for clinical use, be readily accessible and integrated into clinical workflows. Please see Appendix I for a detailed description of this “**resolve VUS**” goal.

Figure 1. Generating variant effect data in the ~1,000 highest need disease-associated genes would drive resolution of ~70% of VUS. **a.** A bubble plot showing the number of single nucleotide VUS in ClinVar (accessed January 1, 2025) by gene size and tests offered in the NIH Genetic Testing Registry (accessed March 28th, 2025), annotated by whether an experimental variant effect map is available for each gene. **b.** A plot showing the cumulative number of VUS in ClinVar (accessed January 1, 2025) that would be captured after assaying all missense variants in genes encoding proteins <600 amino acids in length up to the given rank (by VUS density) for genes with at least moderate evidence (GenCC, accessed January 1, 2025) for disease association. The dashed line shows the number of VUS covered if a variant effect map were available for the 1000 highest-ranked genes.

A second goal is to build a foundational dataset designed to vastly improve computational model-based inference of the molecular mechanism by which a variant causes disease, in other words, its pathomechanism. We define pathomechanism as the set of molecular and cellular phenotypes that can be perturbed by variants and lead to disease. Achieving this goal is important for a variety of reasons. One reason is that understanding variant pathomechanism is critical for developing or deploying variant-guided therapy. A second reason is that, while both *in silico* variant effect predictors and ‘holistic’ functional assays may identify all variants that damage any function of a gene product, deficits in some functions may not yield clinical pathogenicity. A third reason is to accurately classify variants in the ~40% of disease-associated genes that are associated with two or more diseases through different pathomechanisms. Unlike resolving VUS in genes with only a single disease association, where a variant may be classified as having a normal or abnormal result in an assay that interrogates a key function, achieving this goal requires characterizing each variant’s effect on the many layers of molecular (e.g. transcription; splicing; and protein folding, localization and function) and cellular

(transcriptome, signalome, cell internal organization and behavior) function in disparate cell and tissue contexts. As such, the combinatorial space is far too large to experimentally assess every variant for every function in every context, so a model-driven approach is needed. Thus, achieving this goal will require (i) developing novel assays to interrogate the effect of variants across the entire phenotypic ‘stack’ (e.g. molecular, cellular, tissue, etc) in a variety of genetic and environmental contexts; (ii) deploying these assays to ~100 genes with complex or poorly understood pathomechanisms; and (iii) development of predictive models that yield a deeper understanding of how variants perturb molecular and cellular function. Please see Appendix II for a detailed description of this “*model pathomechanism*” goal.

Successful accomplishment of both of these goals would yield a draft atlas with both breadth, in the sense that ~1,000 clinically relevant genes would have the data needed to massively reduce VUS, and depth, in the sense that deep mechanistic characterization of variants in ~100 genes and their regulatory elements would enable generalizable predictive modeling and illuminate paths to the development of variant-guided therapies.

In addition to data generation and predictive modeling efforts needed to achieve these twin goals, a draft atlas effort will require technology development, data coordination and standards as well as a clinical translation effort. Thus, the roadmap presented below is organized into four areas where effort and innovation are needed: data production, technology, infrastructure and standards, and clinical translation.

A roadmap to a draft atlas by 2030

Goal 1: Resolve VUS

	Early (1-3y)	Middle (4-5y)	Beyond 2030
Data production	Data for 100-200 genes	Data for 1000 genes	Data for all disease genes
Technology	Deliver cost-reducing, scale-increasing assays	Implement low-cost assays for genes with many VUS	Assays for every type of variant in every gene
Coordination	Production planning, curation and data standards	Uniform data analysis, MaveDB federation	MaveDB sustainment, analysis platform
Clinical translation	Revise MAVE clinical guidance, clinical data curation plan	Expanded clinical truth sets, automated curation, training	Gene-disease relationships, penetrance, expressivity

Goal 2: Model variant pathomechanism

	Early (1-3y)	Middle (4-5y)	Beyond 2030
Data production	Data for 10-20 genes	Data for 100 genes, inference of some pathomechanisms	High-quality pathomechanism inference for all variants
Technology	Assays that capture cell/tissue context, pathomechanism	Inference of cell/tissue context, pathomechanism	Foundation model for variant effects
Coordination	Modeling/data production coordination	Model repository, benchmarking, integration	Resource sustainment
Clinical translation	Pilot 1-3 genes, target druggable pathomechanisms	10-20 genes, target druggable pathomechanisms	Mechanism-aware therapy broadly deployed

The goal of this document is to lay out a roadmap that catalyses a community-wide effort to produce the draft atlas described above by 2030. The roadmap describes activities in four key areas: data production; technology; infrastructure and standards; and clinical translation. In each area, descriptions of needed activities are preceded by a brief description of the current state of affairs (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. A schematic showing the data production, experimental and predictive technology, coordination and clinical

translation deliverables for the atlas effort.

For each activity, we present the need that motivates the activity, highlight ongoing work in the area, estimate the required effort in terms of number of groups and FTE. We also articulate milestones for the early (years

1-3), middle (years 4-5) and late (beyond 2030) phases of the activity. The descriptions of each activity in this document are summaries. A detailed explanation of each activity will be developed and linked to the corresponding summary.

Data production

We are in the first few years of scaling multiplexed assays of variant effect for production. Production efforts are underway within several centers (including within the NHGRI IGVF Consortium, at the Wellcome Sanger Institute and other sites), where the assays most amenable to scaling (e.g. ddPCA, saturation genome editing, VAMP-seq, MPRA) are being scaled. Thus far, these efforts have yielded a significant increase in the availability of multiplexed functional data and, currently, clinically usable variant effect data for ~50 human genes exists. We estimate that the current annual production capacity for clinical-grade variant effect data around the world is ~50 genes (~20 Wellcome Sanger; ~15 IGVF, primarily University of Washington; ~10 other). Thus, tens of millions of variants in ~1,000 genes must be assessed.

To address this need, we envision dividing efforts according to scale, as has been successful for other consortia (e.g. International Cancer Genome Consortium and The Cancer Genome Atlas). To achieve the **“resolve VUS”** goal, large-scale, centralized efforts based on a small number of production facilities that can apply one or several assays to tens or hundreds of genes a year will be essential as only they can achieve the needed scale. To achieve the **“model pathomechanism”** goal, medium-scale, networked efforts focused on diving deeply into defined sets of genes or particular model systems and involving several labs with complementary expertise will be required. These large- and medium-scale efforts will be complemented and supplemented by small-scale, decentralized efforts in individual labs that develop and apply bespoke assays to genes that are not amenable to scaled assays but are of high clinical relevance. This data production landscape highlights the need for coordinated production, especially across efforts operating at different scales, as well as data standards and data curation/storage/dissemination, detailed in the “Coordination, infrastructure and standards” section below.

Large-scale, centralized data production efforts

Achieving the **“resolve VUS”** goal requires generating functional data for variants in ~1,000 genes by deploying a small set of informative core assays in a gene- and disease-agnostic way. The current pace of data generation, particularly in assays conducted on full length proteins and genes in human cells falls far short of what is needed to deliver a draft atlas. As described in the Technology section below, we envision that technology development will deliver considerable cost reductions and scale increases that will increase the pace of data production. However, even with these improvements, large-scale data production efforts will remain a critical component of atlas creation. Large-scale efforts capture efficiencies of scale including negotiating contracts for the purchase of key reagents and synthetic DNA libraries, training and retention of specialized personnel and automation of laboratory and computational processes. Lack of investment in large-scale data production threatens the **“resolve VUS”** goal, in particular, where the standardized application of a small set of best-in-class assays to a very large number of genes is required.

Ongoing work: Nascent large-scale efforts exist at the Wellcome Sanger Institute and University of Washington Variant Effects Program. The current production capacity of the Wellcome Sanger Institute is ~25 genes per year using the saturation genome editing method. The current production capacity of the University of Washington Variant Effects Program is ~15 genes per year using saturation genome editing and LABEL-seq.

Approximate effort required: Large (e.g. 4 production centers with ~15 FTE each, plus a coordination effort)

Early phase milestones

- Agreement upon core assays that will be deployed for large-scale production efforts
- Draft quality standards and analysis pipelines for each assay
- Draft of community-led, model-guided gene prioritization (see [Appendix III](#))
- Framework for formal coordination of production schedules
- Delivery of pilot-scale (10-50 genes per effort) data, with overlap between efforts to assess reproducibility
- Design and pilot testing of data annotation and dissemination infrastructure

Middle phase milestones

- Production-ready standards and analysis pipelines for each assay
- Production-scale data generation (50-100+ genes/yr per effort)
- Refinement and finalization of data annotation and dissemination infrastructure
- Integration of cost-reducing and scale increasing technologies
- Integration of newly developed core assays

Late phase

- Analysis of lessons learned and articulation of a plan for a complete atlas

Medium-scale, networked data production efforts

The "**model pathomechanism**" goal requires the deployment of more specialized assays to capture different molecular and cellular aspects of variant function in different cell, genetic and environmental contexts on a focused set of ~100 genes. Achieving this goal requires combining biological expertise in a subset of the genes chosen and also the ability to deploy newly-developed MAVEs focused on measuring variant effects on different pathomechanisms and in different cell, genetic and environmental contexts. Because these data are being generated with the explicit goal of creating context-aware variant effect prediction models, close partnership with modelers is also needed. These needs are best met in medium-scale production efforts organized around particular diseases or particular types of genes where a focused set of contexts are known/relevant. Moreover, these efforts work best when they include labs with expertise on the relevant genes, model systems and contexts.

Ongoing work: A few medium-scale production efforts have been initiated and have demonstrated efficacy, although their work is largely uncoordinated and not focused on capturing mechanistic and contextual detail. There are several medium-scale efforts, an exemplar being the NHLBI-funded CardioVar center. CardioVar seeks to illuminate the molecular mechanisms of cardiovascular disease-related variants using a variety of MAVEs, and includes experts in cardiovascular disease-related biology, gene function and clinical implementation.

Approximate effort required: Medium (e.g. 10 groups with ~6 FTE each)

Early phase milestones

- Draft of community-led, model-guided gene prioritization (see [Appendix III](#)). For the "**model pathomechanism**" goal, prioritization will need to include intensive collaboration with biologists, clinicians, drug developers and modelers to ensure that the mechanisms/contexts chosen are appropriate.
- Delivery of pilot-scale data (1-2 genes per effort)

Middle phase milestones

- Production-scale data generation (3-5 genes/yr per effort)
- Integration of cost-reducing and scale increasing technologies
- Integration of newly developed mechanism- and context-aware assays

Late phase

- Analysis of lessons learned, including estimation of additional data needed to enable accurate model-based inference of variant pathomechanism for all genes

Small-scale, decentralized data production efforts

Most variant effect data has, so far, been produced in individual labs focusing on one or a handful of genes. The strengths of this small-scale data production model is the ability to develop bespoke assays and analyses deeply informed by the biology of the particular gene or disease being studied. The weaknesses of small scale efforts are that they cannot scale to the thousands of variant effect datasets required for a draft atlas and that data from labs doing small-scale production work can be more challenging to standardize and can vary in quality.

Both the large- and medium-scale data production efforts we envision will focus on applying a limited set of assays, beginning with the genes with high VUS density and clinical need, and where existing or under-development assays can provide useful data. However, genes of high biological and, in some cases, clinical importance will not be amenable to these large- and medium-scale efforts. These include genes where compelling biological questions exist but the clinical need is lower or uncertain, and genes with high need but where no existing or under-development generalizable assay is applicable. Moreover, even after large- and medium-scale production efforts have generated variant effect maps for a particular gene, there may be a need to generate additional maps under diverse conditions (e.g. stress, drug treatment, etc) or for specific phenotypes.

Ongoing work: Small scale variant effect data generation efforts have been underway for approximately a decade. In the past five years, these efforts have begun to be coordinated via the AVE Alliance. We conservatively estimate that ~dozens of labs around the world are undertaking the production of at least one variant effect map.

These efforts are not necessarily focused on furnishing variant effect data for clinical purposes but instead are often motivated by a particular biological question. Nonetheless, such data can be hugely impactful when shared with appropriate metadata. These efforts are funded by a large diversity of sources.

Approximate effort required: As described above, dozens of individual labs are already contributing to an atlas. Funding of large-scale production centers cannot replace this small-scale, investigator-initiated work, which is often bespoke to a particular gene, mechanism or biological question. Thus, investment in these efforts by individual labs should be sustained. However, investment in infrastructure, standards, curation and community organization is needed to coordinate and capture these efforts (see [Coordination, infrastructure and standards section](#)).

Early phase milestones

- Integration of small-scale data producers into the planning of production
- Pilot-scale modeling efforts to determine how data from small-scale producers can best be standardized
- Pilot incentive program for early and high-quality data deposition

Middle phase milestones

- Adoption of description of experiments and standards for sharing and quality control of data, as measured by at least 50% of publications appearing from small efforts adhering to such standards
- Empowering of the small-scale production community by open sharing and teaching of new variant effect mapping technologies

Late phase

- Analysis of lessons learned, particularly regarding the added value of small-scale, focused assays when general assay results and predictions are available

Technology

A first generation of mature multiplexed assays of variant effect have been developed and are already widely deployed. These first-generation methods employ comparatively simple model systems and assays. Examples include assays in human cancer cell lines (e.g. saturation genome editing, VAMP-seq, MPRA), yeast (e.g. complementation, ddPCA) or molecular display. In general, first-generation assays read out phenotypes that are easy to measure (e.g. cell growth or protein abundance) in comparatively low-complexity model systems (e.g. yeast, human cancer cell lines). These assays have been highly successful in generating clinical-grade variant effect data that can dramatically reduce VUS for genes where they can be applied. However, they typically measure a variant's effect on only one phenotype or do not differentiate between phenotypes, thus providing limited insight into pathomechanism. Moreover, they cannot be applied to all clinically important genes and will require additional development to reduce cost and increase scale.

Computational variant effect predictors use evolutionary and structural information about a variant to predict a variant's effect. Current variant effect predictors are highly accurate when benchmarked against clinical control variants. This high accuracy is the result of the use of more sophisticated modeling approaches, availability of more control pathogenic and benign variants and the rise of metapredictors. Limitations of current predictors are that they generally predict only simple, generalized function (e.g. normal or abnormal) without respect to mechanism or cell context; that evaluating their accuracy can be challenging owing to model circularity or lack of control variants; and that many predictors make predictions for a limited set of variants (only for some genes, only for coding variants, not for complex alleles such as deletions or multiple substitutions, etc).

Variant effects can be experimentally measured and predicted at scale, and our vision for a draft 2030 atlas integrates both experiments and predictions. Relative to the "**resolve VUS**" goal, experimental measurements and predictions are considered independent lines of evidence and thus can be combined for the purposes of classifying a clinical variant. Thus, having high-quality experiments and predictions for every variant will lead to resolution of the most VUS. For this goal, experimental technology development is needed to increase the scale and reduce costs of making variant effect measurements. Modeling technology development is needed to enable accurate prediction of noncoding and complex allele variant effects.

Relative to the "**model pathomechanism**" goal, multiplexed assay development is needed to effectively capture variant effects in the correct cell/tissue/developmental, genetic and environmental contexts. Moreover, multiplexed assay development is needed to read out the many mechanistically informative layers of phenotype in a tractable way (e.g. molecular phenotypes like splicing, protein folding, localization and function; cellular phenotypes like transcriptome and signalome state, internal organization, behavior). However, the space formed by these contexts and phenotypes is effectively infinite. Thus, modeling technology is needed that can leverage sparse experimental measurement of variant effects to predict effects across contexts and phenotypes.

Improving the scalability and reducing the costs of multiplexed assays of variant effect

Based on a small survey of AVE Alliance labs, making a variant effect measurement currently costs ~\$10-\$35 USD. Achieving the goal of measuring the effect of all possible ~6,000 single nucleotide variants in each of ~1,000 genes using current technologies would thus cost between ~\$100M and ~\$350M USD. Creating an atlas encompassing most genes in the genome and their attendant regulatory regions would cost at least an order of magnitude more if current methods were used. Thus, significant cost reductions are required. In addition to experimentally-rooted cost reduction strategies, target prioritization based on predictive modeling should be explored to reduce the burden of experiments required.

Ongoing work: Work to increase scale and reduce costs is happening in a few individual labs and centers, particularly focused on frequently used assays (e.g. SGE, human and yeast reporters). But there has not been coordination on this topic yet. Development of new automation platforms in industry is underway, especially for assays involving mammalian cell culture. But these new platforms have not been tested for high-throughput comprehensive functional characterisation of genetic variation in disease-relevant genes.

Approximate effort required: Medium (e.g. 4 groups with 3 FTE each, plus a coordination effort)

Early phase milestones

- Accurate estimation of per-variant costs of current MAVEs, including comparisons across existing labs practicing these methods
- Workshop focused on identifying of cost- or scale-constraining steps that are common to many MAVEs
- Development of coordination and industry partnerships to reduce costs (e.g. library sharing, dedicated, large-scale purchases of reagents)
- Trialing of automation to reduce costs and increase scale for select assays
- Form modeler-production center partnerships; delivery of a pilot plan for model-guided, cost-reduced production

Middle phase milestones

- Deliver on cost-reduction strategy for steps that are common to many MAVEs
- Develop first-generation cost-reduced versions of a handful of key MAVEs
- Hand-off of cost-reduced versions of key MAVEs in production centers
- Production center implementation of automated workflows
- Conclusion of modeler-production center partnerships, delivery of an at-scale model-guided production plan

Late phase

- Delivery of transformative cost-reducing technologies (e.g. library synthesis, different types of assays explicitly designed for high scale/low cost, etc)

Developing assays and predictive models that capture variant effects in the correct cell, tissue, developmental, genetic and environmental contexts

The need for new context-aware assays arises partially from the fact that the first generation of technologies cannot be applied to all genes with appreciable VUS because these assays do not capture sufficient context to make sensible variant effect measurements. Examples of genes where current technologies fail include those that act only in specialized cell types and those that drive non cell-autonomous processes. Likewise, currently available predictive models largely ignore context. The need for new multiplexed assays and predictive models is hinted at by recent work that has shown that pathogenic variant penetrance is lower than previously

understood. For example, only a minority of individuals carrying pathogenic variants in large biobanks actually have disease, suggesting that genetic and environmental context play in making accurate, genetically-guided predictions of disease risk. However, our understanding of the importance of context on variant effects is partial. Thus, related to the “**resolve VUS**” goal, some clinically important genes will require new technology that can measure variant effects in known-relevant contexts at scale to render clinically useful data. Related to the “modeling mechanism” goal, new technologies are needed to discover the degree to which variant effects depend on context. Then, experimental measurements and predictions must be made such that variant effects can be understood with respect to specific, biologically relevant contexts.

Ongoing work: Development of multiplexed assays that capture context is ongoing at a small scale in individual labs and also in a few medium-scale efforts (e.g. NHGRI’s CEGS, Broad, etc). However, these efforts are disconnected and incomplete. Context specific predictive models are largely nonexistent, although work in this area in the noncoding space has begun to emerge.

Approximate effort required: Medium (e.g. 4 groups with ~5 FTE each, plus a coordination effort)

Early phase milestones

- Discovery, tracking and knitting together of ongoing efforts
- Enumeration of important contexts (e.g. “what are the important cell type(s) for each VUS-bearing gene?”, “which VUS-bearing genes must be assessed in multicellular contexts?”, “which genes have evidence of low penetrance? high?”).
- Prioritization of contexts based on VUS need
- Delivery and benchmarking of technologies currently in development for capturing variants in the correct cell/tissue/developmental, genetic and environmental contexts
- Develop first-generation predictive models that can make cell type-specific and genetic background-dependent predictions of variant effect

Middle phase milestones

- Pressure test of the experimental technologies delivered in the early phase by applying them to a handful of genes, with the goal of exploring the strength and nature of variant context dependence
- Develop additional experimental methods to serve contexts that are deemed important and remain unmet needs based on early-phase work
- Refine context-aware predictive models and benchmark them by comparing to the first few experimental data sets and to other sources of information
- Development of cross-context variant effect predictions (e.g. context transfer of experimental variant effect data)

Late phase

- Hand off mature context-aware experimental methods to production centers and the broader research community
- Integrate the early and middle phase assessment of contexts that need to be captured with regards to VUS-bearing genes with the ability of context-aware models to predict context-dependent effects to design and prioritize genes for a production-scale campaign

Developing assays that can capture variant effects across the stack of phenotypes

Cell-based phenotypes can be thought of as forming a ‘stack’, with a variant impacting one or many levels of the stack. On the molecular level, phenotypes may align with the central dogma, e.g., impacting transcription, splicing or transcript stability, or altering protein folding, localization or function. On the cellular level, they can

alter cell state by changing the transcriptome, proteome or signalome. Or, they can alter the ultrastructural and organellar internal organization of the cell, or cell behavior. However, the first generation of MAVEs have measured only a handful of phenotypes. In particular, much of the currently available and planned variant effect data comes from cell growth assays which do not provide insight into which phenotypes are disrupted. Likewise, predictive models, with few exceptions, cannot provide insight into pathomechanism. However, in order to understand variant biology and create precision genomic medicines, a comprehensive understanding of how variants alter phenotype is required. Variant-guided therapies that either depend on or can be improved by phenotypic knowledge include targeted kinase inhibitors, antisense oligos and protein folding corrector drugs. Thus, new multiplexed assays and predictive models that can capture variant effects across the stack of phenotypes are critical for delivering on the “modeling mechanism” goal and the promise of the atlas for variant-guided diagnostics and therapies.

Phenotypic space is effectively infinite. Therefore, we will constrain our efforts by identifying and focusing on phenotypes that are either common to at least some pathogenic variants or targeted by variant-guided therapies.

Ongoing work: Development of multiplexed assays that capture context is ongoing at a small scale in individual labs and also in a few medium-scale efforts. However, these efforts are disconnected and incomplete. Mechanism-aware predictive models are largely nonexistent, although work in this area has emerged for some mechanisms such as loss of protein stability.

Approximate effort required: Medium (e.g. 4 groups with ~5 FTE each, plus a coordination effort)

Early phase milestones

- Discovery, tracking and knitting together of ongoing efforts
- Enumeration of important phenotypes of pathogenic variant effect
- Enumeration of molecular and cellular phenotypes that can inform the development of variant-guided therapies
- Delivery and benchmarking of technologies currently in development for measuring variant phenotype
- Develop first-generation models that can make phenotype-aware predictions

Middle phase milestones

- Pressure test of the experimental technologies delivered in the early phase by applying them to a handful of genes in service of the “modeling pathomechanism” goal.
- Develop additional experimental methods to serve phenotypes that are deemed important and remain unmet needs based on early-phase work
- Refine phenotype-aware predictive models and benchmark them by comparing to the first few experimental data sets and to other sources of information
- Development of variant effect predictions (e.g. context transfer of experimental variant effect data)

Late phase

- Hand off mature mechanism-aware experimental methods to production centers
- Integrate the early and middle phase assessment of mechanisms that need to be captured with the ability of context-aware models to predict mechanism to design and prioritize genes for a production-scale campaign

Coordination, infrastructure and standards

Coordinating data generation; constructing a robust infrastructure for sharing, discovering and using multiplexed functional data; and standardizing and benchmarking data are critical to realizing both the “**resolve VUS**” and “**model pathomechanism**” goals of a draft 2030 atlas. So far, the community has not prioritized target genes or developed a plan for which assays should be applied to which genes, although individual researchers have developed such schemes. A community-driven target prioritization effort could maximize return on investment by ordering production in an efficient manner, focusing work on the highest-value assays and connecting data producers to data consumers. With respect to coordinating production that is underway, [MaveRegistry](#) is a tool for researchers to announce their intent to generate multiplexed functional data for a particular gene or set of genes. But this tool is used by only a subset of data generators meaning that data production efforts are largely uncoordinated, except between the few existing large-scale data production efforts.

Relative to infrastructure for data exploration and dissemination, MaveDB is a database initially launched as a data warehouse with a user-driven model of data submission. Currently, MaveDB contains ~8.5 million variant effects from 2,667 datasets (4/2/25, [mavedb.org/statistics](#)) and has ~850 active users monthly. The data in MaveDB have largely been curated by volunteers on the MaveDB team, with few researchers choosing to upload their data. However, most of the datasets in MaveDB lack the metadata and annotations that would empower re-use, both clinically and for AI/ML approaches. MaveDB has recently added a full-featured API and limited data exploration and discovery capabilities, with more work planned to enhance these capabilities as well as to facilitate use by practicing clinicians. However, the community lacks a complete solution for data discovery and exploration, analogous to a genome browser or the gnomAD front end.

A variety of groups have articulated standards for the generation, sharing and clinical use of experimental variant effect data, including efforts by AVE, ClinGen and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH). These standards aim to ensure that each multiplexed functional dataset is of sufficient quality and published with sufficient metadata to be useful to others. However, the different standards published so far are not fully in agreement and, more pressingly, are not generally adhered to. As a consequence, most MAVE data remains difficult to curate and re-use, particularly clinically.

The [Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance](#) (AVE) has emerged as the key organization working to coordinate efforts, build infrastructure and set standards. AVE is a grass-roots, international effort encompassing over 700 researchers and clinicians from over 50 countries focused on understanding the effect of variants at nucleotide resolution. AVE has led development of a variety of community resources, core infrastructure and international data standards. For example, AVE coordinates MaveDB and MaveRegistry, and also organizes the annual Mutational Scanning Symposium. AVE works with a diverse group of international clinically-oriented organizations key to realizing the “**resolve VUS**” goal, particularly IGVF, ClinGen, GA4GH, and DECIPHER. Because of AVE’s significant leadership, track record and existing infrastructure, we envision that AVE will play a leading role in coordinating and supporting the global community in the realization of the draft 2030 atlas. The global nature and programmatic complexity of the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance necessitates professional staff to manage, support, organize and coordinate the activities of its members, multiple work streams and committees. The current executive office of AVE comprises one part-time program manager and one part-time program operations specialist.

Coordination of gene prioritization and production efforts

Our roadmap envisions a large number of small-scale production efforts combining with medium- and large-scale efforts to generate the data comprising the draft 2030 atlas. In order to maximize the efficiency of

production, avoid overlaps and ensure that the highest-need genes are served first, improved production coordination is required. Assays should also be analyzed and matched with each prioritized gene. Moreover, production efforts operating at different scales should share knowledge, protocols, tools and reagents. Such coordination must be international in nature and has two key components: community-driven prioritization of genes for production and coordination between labs.

Ongoing work: The atlas effort already involves a large number of small-scale and a handful of medium-scale producers. Coordinated gene prioritization has not yet happened, although researchers within AVE have individually created priority lists. AVE maintains MaveRegistry, which contains ~200 individual projects registered. But well over 50% of multiplexed functional datasets are published having never been registered, and unintentional redundancy is, unfortunately, still a reality. Intentional redundancy can be highly desirable in large-scale collaborative genomic initiatives, especially in early stages, to understand and ensure data quality and reproducibility. However, in later stages, unintentional redundancy can represent a waste of resources and can complicate downstream use of the data being generated.

Approximate effort required: Small (e.g. ~2 FTE within AVE)

Early phase milestones

- Develop principles for gene and assay prioritization (see [Appendix III](#))
 - Convene an AVE-led gene and assay prioritization working group
 - Model-guided draft gene prioritization
 - Community-led refinement of gene prioritization, via a one-day workshop
- Coordination of ongoing data production
 - Convene an AVE-led production coordination working group
 - Develop and publish a MaveRegistry development roadmap
 - Internal review of current MaveRegistry features
 - Survey of data producers to understand what is preventing them from sharing their plans
 - Outreach to all past and current known data producers to request that they participate in MaveRegistry
 - Explore funder-driven requirement to use MaveRegistry
- Delivery of critical MaveRegistry features, including integration with MaveDB and other resources to boost project visibility

Middle phase milestones

- Completion of MaveRegistry roadmap, bug fixes, feature requests
- Ongoing outreach to producers to stay engaged with MaveRegistry
- Ongoing updating of gene prioritization list, both in terms of completed genes and in terms of refinement of ordering/addition of new genes

Late phase

- Maintenance of MaveRegistry, with plans to sunset as production draws to a close

Data coordination and dissemination

The draft 2030 atlas will be defined by the experimental data and model-based predictions, and these data must be stored with appropriate metadata to enable diverse downstream use cases. Additionally, the atlas will require a navigable frontend and federation with other resources that biologists and clinicians already use to learn about genes and variants. We envision a single, authoritative source for functional data that extends MaveDB to include not just MAVEs, but non-saturation medium-throughput assays, as well as a

complementary database for large-scale prediction data. These resources would federate directly with well-established resources like ClinGen and UniProt, as well as emerging efforts such as the IGVF Catalogue that will provide valuable additional context.

Currently, MaveDB is the database of record for variant effect data. MaveDB is built using open-source software commonly found in enterprise applications (PostgreSQL, FastAPI, Vue.js), resulting in a scalable and maintainable platform for future growth and feature development. The database has a fully-featured API that enables automated data access and deposition for expert users. The web-based front end is designed to guide new users through data and metadata submission, and provides a variety of automatically-generated visualizations and supports links to explore data externally using tools such as the UCSC Genome Browser. Variant effect prediction models are not currently archived in any central location, but many provide precomputed results or trained models via the authors' website or GitHub, and some are aggregated in large datasets such as OpenCRAVAT, EnsemblVEP and VIPdb.

Approximate effort required: Medium (e.g. 1 group with ~10 FTE)

Early phase milestones

- Revise MaveDB roadmap in light of this expanded scope to include:
 - Support for base and prime editor MAVES
 - Improved support for large non-MAVE functional datasets (e.g., high-throughput patch clamp assays)
 - Rich comparisons of multiple functional datasets on the same targets
- Improve curation of external identifiers (e.g., UniProt and RefSeq accessions) to support federation
- Assess suitability of OpenCRAVAT, EnsemblVEP and VIPdb as partners to store variant effect predictions and required metadata.
 - Coordinate with these databases and researchers generating variant effect predictions to develop data and metadata models
 - Determine feasibility and need for creating a new database for predictor data, based on the MaveDB codebase.
- Engage with data producers to support curation of new datasets into MaveDB, as well as in-house curation from published papers
- Create new visualizations based on federated data, such as protein structure-based views and automatic comparisons with clinical and population genetic data
- Perform focus group testing to help define user need and prioritize feature development

Middle phase milestones

- Build more sophisticated tools for MaveDB curators to update user-submitted datasets via the web interface
- Generate mappings to non-human model organism genomes to allow more researchers to benefit from data generated on human genes
- Develop and launch a companion interface that enables detailed comparison of experimental data from MaveDB with model output
- Ongoing engagement with data producers and curation

Late phase

- Analysis of lessons learned and articulation of a plan for ongoing support for any community data resources that have become essential
- Develop model for sustainment of resource

Uniform data analysis

The diversity of experimental technologies employed to generate MAVE and other types of functional data has led to a fragmented data analysis landscape. While some dedicated tools exist, most notably Enrich2 and DiMSum, many datasets are processed using ad hoc scripts that are not easily maintained, audited, or reused. Differences in the statistical approaches used to calculate variant functional scores have also been identified as a major impediment to using these datasets for machine learning and AI based analysis, as it makes the datasets even more challenging to combine. Uniform data processing is essential to ensure that data are AI-ready.

There is therefore an opportunity to produce a flexible data analysis pipeline that can be used to reanalyze existing datasets and shared broadly to enable data production efforts at all scales. We envision a robust, open source software tool that can analyze most datasets generated to date, as well as new experimental designs that we can anticipate. The approach should also be scalable and simplify the generation of datasets that comply with key data and metadata standards.

Ongoing work: Researchers within AVE have developed a new software framework called CountESS for analyzing MAVE and other functional assay data using a modular architecture that supports built-in as well as third-party plugins. CountESS is built in Python and uses DuckDB to handle larger-than-memory datasets performantly. At present, the tool can support several common pipelines for MAVEs and is being used by early adopters in research labs. Additionally, the community has developed several modern statistical methods that build on innovations from transcriptomics and other fields that should be leveraged more broadly.

Approximate effort required: Major development for CountESS has been completed, but implementation of pipelines for diverse experiments and reanalysis of existing data using a shared statistical model will require small investment (1 group with ~4 FTE).

Early phase milestones

- First public release of the CountESS framework
- Identification of a shared statistical method for each major class of dataset
- Identification of experimental designs that will be supported with prebuilt pipelines
- Consultation to identify and catalog near future data analysis challenges
- Identification of key datasets to reanalyze from raw data

Middle phase milestones

- Implementation of example CountESS pipelines for identified experimental designs
- Comprehensive documentation including tutorials for data generation centers
- Reanalysis of historical raw experimental data using the shared statistical method and associated pipeline to produce a uniform, standardized dataset

Late phase milestones

- Deliver a large standardized dataset that has been analyzed using shared statistical methods
- Share lessons learned from this reanalysis effort, including guidance on sharing experimental metadata to enable recomputability and reproducibility for future data generation efforts

Data standards, curation and benchmarking

Standards and curation are required to make variant effect data useful, and benchmarking is necessary to assess experimental and predictive methods and reveal what comprises high-quality data. Standards, curation

and benchmarking are particularly important for the atlas effort because we envision that the atlas will be an amalgam of experimental data generated by large-, medium- and small-scale producers around the globe along with models that ingest, transform or are combined with the experimental data. Realizing this vision is only possible if all data within the atlas has a shared format for data and associated metadata. Additionally, our experience is that even with clear, easy-to-follow standards, active curation will still be required for some datasets. Thus, the key parts of this effort are: 1) refining existing standards; 2) working to ensure that data producers and modelers can easily adhere to standards; 3) curation of data that does not conform to standards; and 4) constructing benchmarking frameworks for experimental and predictive methods and data.

Work by AVE has resulted in a minimum information standard for MAVEs that is being extended to support new types of data. These minimum information standards are now the basis for MaveDB metadata, and data submitters are guided through a web form collecting the required information. Large-scale curation performed as part of IGVF consortium activities has informed an updated version of the minimum information standards. The IGVF data portal supports highly complementary standards and metadata, focused on a granular representation of raw data that enables long-term archiving and reanalysis of consortium datasets. GA4GH is an important international genomic standards body, particularly for clinical translation applications, and MaveDB has been collaborating with key GA4GH members to implement and develop standards for functional data, which are now being adopted and implemented by MaveDB and ClinVar. AVE has also developed guidelines for releasing a variant effect predictor, which can form the basis for a more prescriptive and robust minimum information standard.

Work by AVE and AVE members has yielded initial benchmarking resources and results. New experimental and predictive variant effect data are typically benchmarked against clinical variants of known effect, with performance on these variants considered to be revealing of data quality and utility. Work benchmarking experimental data with model predictions and vice versa is less well developed. Here, a handful of manuscripts describing predictive models (e.g. EVE and AlphaMissense) have benchmarked model performance using experimental variant effect data. The ProteinGym resource contains experimental variant effect data along with the metadata needed for predictive model benchmarking. Moreover, ProteinGym includes the performance of ~70 models in predicting the experimental data. However, work to date has focused on using experiments to benchmark models, with little work in the opposite direction. And, no concerted effort has been made to compare different MAVE experimental technologies or informatics tools using a rigorous benchmarking framework.

Approximate effort required: Medium (e.g. 3 groups with ~2 FTE)

Early phase milestones

- Refine existing metadata standards for experiments
- Articulate and refine minimum information standards for variant effect predictions, building on [established AVE guidance](#)
- Coordinate outreach and engagement about standards
- Build a data curation team and demonstrate that they can apply the standards to pilot data (matched MAVEs and predictions for 50-100 genes)
- Convene a group of modelers and experimentalists to develop a benchmarking framework for experimental and predictive methods
- Benchmark a subset of existing predictive models and experimental methods using the framework with the goal of identifying high-performing methods

Middle phase milestones

- Construction of automated tools for evaluating submission compliance within MaveDB, including a shareable publishable artifact like a metadata certificate
- Continue promoting standards adoption across federated genomics resources that want to access MaveDB data
- Develop new clinically-oriented data standards for computational model output based on existing GA4GH standards for experimental functional data
- Extend implementation of human-centric (e.g., GA4GH) standards to support data generated for non-human targets and the application of human MAVE data to non-human model systems
- Build automated, prospective benchmarking of experimental variant effect data with models and vice versa into MaveDB

Late phase

- Analysis of lessons learned and articulation of a plan for long-term standards maintenance, under the auspices of AVE, GA4GH or another suitable organization

Training a global community of researchers that can effectively produce and use functional data

In order to help the global research community benefit from the atlas and the technology that underpins it, a sharing, training and education effort is needed. Furthermore, as we pursue the many goals of scaling up existing assays and developing new methods for accessing diverse phenotypes, we will develop expertise that should be articulated and shared broadly. We envision sharing protocols and reagents; training researchers; and empowering new and existing research programs all over the world. Training materials such as protocols and webinars with a very low barrier to entry, as well as more involved programs involving site visits and in-person training courses, are needed.

Ongoing work: The annual Mutational Scanning Symposium includes a day of programming set aside for sharing methodological advances, and the recordings of these talks have been very popular with several having thousands of views on YouTube. Work is underway to develop a multiplexed assay training course in collaboration with Wellcome Connecting Science, but it is still early days.

Approximate effort required: Small (1 group with ~2 FTE each, plus a substantial travel budget to support visiting instructors and bursaries for scientists from LMICs)

Early phase milestones

- Create an AVE education working group that combines researchers focusing on assay development with scientific education and outreach experts
- Landscape analysis of existing protocols and training resources
- Develop a hub of established training resources (protocols, videos, slide decks, etc.) and identify where the major gaps are and what formats are most successful

Medium phase milestones

- Develop new training materials for well-established multiplexed assay systems
- Liaise with technology development experts to formulate external-facing guidance on how to develop new assay systems
- Plan and deliver training workshops globally, either as standalone events or as satellite events for well-established scientific meetings

Late phase milestones

- Analysis of training outcomes and lessons learned for further education activities

Clinical translation

Creation of a draft atlas will empower many dimensions of genomic medicine. Relative to the “**resolve VUS**” goal, multiplexed functional data has been increasingly incorporated into clinical variant interpretation workflows. A key enabler for the use of multiplexed functional data in variant classification is the 2020 release by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation (SVI) of the OddsPath framework, which provides a rigorous way to weight and incorporate functional data when classifying variants. With this new guidance in place, several groups demonstrated that high-quality multiplexed functional data could provide strong evidence, and that inclusion of such evidence in variant classification workflows could sharply reduce the rate of VUS. Likewise, researchers, industry and clinicians have articulated draft guidance for executing and reporting high-quality MAVEs for clinical use. These developments make it clear that multiplexed functional data can increase the yield of genetic diagnostic assays, and that a draft atlas would have a transformative effect on clinical genetics. However, remaining barriers prevent multiplexed functional data from being used to interpret the average variant.

Those barriers are: 1) most genes lack multiplexed functional data; 2) even for genes where multiplexed functional data exists, a “truth set” of variants sufficient for calibrating the strength of evidence under the OddsPath framework may not be available; 3) current guidance does not address all questions around use of multiplexed functional data, e.g., whether and when to separately calibrate different regions of a protein, how to standardize and incorporate measurement error estimates, what to do when multiple sources of functional data are available, and more; 4) even for genes where multiplexed functional data exists and evidence strength can be appropriately calibrated, clinicians and clinical labs cannot now easily discover and use the data.

Relative to the “**model pathomechanism**” goal, understanding variant pathomechanism is a necessary step in developing precision, variant-specific therapies. Even when we know that a variant is pathogenic, we rarely understand how the variant exerts its effect. As a consequence, variant-specific treatments remain almost entirely a distant goal. Exceptions that powerfully illustrate the promise of variant-specific treatments include lumacaftor, a variant-specific small molecule that corrects folding defects in CFTR in cystic fibrosis, and antisense oligonucleotides which are variant-specific, short oligonucleotides that alter gene expression. However, because we do not understand how most pathogenic variants exert their effect, we are unable to develop variant-specific therapies at scale. The draft atlas we envision would enable the development of such therapies at scale, along with clinical evaluation and deployment.

Develop clinical truth sets and update guidance for clinical translation of functional data

Genomic medicine providers analyze variants found via genetic testing using a framework that incorporates different types of evidence to interpret each variant as benign, pathogenic or VUS. Effective use of MAVE-derived functional data or variant effect predictions as a source of evidence requires calibration, a process by which functional scores are translated into evidence for use in clinical variant classification according to rules developed by the ACMG/AMP/ClinGen. The lack of a sufficient number of known pathogenic and benign variants for calibration and unclear guidance regarding what defines these variants of known effect remain a barrier. Further when surveyed, providers across a range of positions and levels of experience expressed discomfort with using multiplexed functional data. As such, expert guidance and dedicated biocurators are required to 1. Update and better define sets of variants with known clinical effects; 2. Update guidance for using multiplexed functional data in the clinic; 3. Provide support for the development of dissemination tools to support the clinical use case; and 4. Provide calibration services to enable clinical use.

Define and update truth sets. The process of calibration for a particular gene-disease pair requires a large truth set comprising many variants classified as pathogenic or benign. Unfortunately, only ~15% of genes with

moderate or stronger links to disease have a sufficiently-sized truth set to reach strong evidence in either the pathogenic or benign direction. To overcome the lack of sufficiently-sized truth sets, new strategies are needed. In many cases, variants of known clinical effect, especially benign variants, could be identified by deeper outreach to clinical labs, ClinGen Expert Panels, patient advocacy groups and researchers testing or studying these genes. For genes where loss-of-function is the primary disease mechanism, nonsense, canonical splice and synonymous variants might be used to augment the truth set. Alternatively, case/control data generated from large biobanks or patient cohorts could be used to demonstrate that functional scores correlate strongly with disease risk, even where no individual variant can be classified confidently. However, understanding when it is appropriate to use the alternative truth sets or translating an alternative validation method into evidence for variant classification is an unsolved problem.

Update guidance for using multiplexed functional data. To empower the clinical community in using functional data, research must be paired with frequently-updated guidance for multiplexed functional data. Such functional data-specific guidance will need to be developed in the context of evolving overall guidance around clinical variant interpretation. For example, the field is awaiting the ACMG/AMP/CAP/ClinGen sequence variant classification version 4 standards (SVCv4) which will necessitate updated guidance for using functional evidence and variant effect predictors.

Calibration methods are evolving to take advantage of the quantitative nature of multiplexed functional data to generate variant-specific evidence strength. These calibration methods need to be thoroughly vetted before guidance can be written to adopt any of the methods for general use. Increasingly, MAVEs are being used to measure multiple aspects of a gene or protein's function, and multimodal MAVEs are also being developed, raising questions about how to combine multiple molecular and cellular phenotype measurements to generate evidence. Finally, the relationship between experimental variant effect data and variant effect predictions must be understood to appropriately combine them.

Data curation, calibration and development of dissemination tools to support the clinical use case. In order to be used in the clinic, functional data must be calibrated. However, there is currently no governing body nor workforce to curate and calibrate functional data as it appears, nor is there an incentive structure to induce individual researchers or clinicians to calibrate the data. Moreover, tools discover functional data and assess data and calibration quality are missing. Thus, to serve the genomic medicine community and realize the goal of fully leveraging functional data for variant classification, curation, dissemination and visualization tools specifically designed for the clinical use case are needed.

Ongoing work: The new ClinGen/AVE Functional Data Working group, which brings together the former AVE Clinical Variant Interpretation workstream with experts from ClinGen and the global genome medicine community, has been tasked with updating guidance for the translation of functional data to evidence strength according to the forthcoming SVCv4 standards. In addition, they plan to work with ClinGen Expert Panels to systematically evaluate functional evidence for specific genes; develop a series of workshops to educate data generators and consumers (described below); and evaluate and provide additional guidance around new methods for evidence strength calibration.

A first-of-its-kind, large-scale curation and calibration effort is underway for ~40 genes within the IGVF consortium, and a new front-end for MaveDB is being developed to share the resulting data and calibrations with clinicians. These efforts may serve as a pilot for the needed curation, calibration and dissemination effort, which will have to function on a massively larger scale.

Approximate effort required: Medium (e.g. 1 groups with ~6-8 FTE) Effort from dedicated biocurators are

essential to curating truth sets and performing the calibration of the functional data to translate it into evidence for variant classification. Project management support is needed to coordinate the ClinGen/AVE Functional Data Working group.

Early phase milestones

- Develop draft guidelines for evaluating the quality of MAVE datasets that includes more definitive guidance on truth sets, and is updated for the SVCv4 standards
- Launch a pilot study to determine how to efficiently gather pathogenic and benign variants for truth sets by working with VCEPs, patient-led organizations and biobanks.
- Assess calibrations performed using nonsense and synonymous variants to those calibrated using gold standard clinical variants.
- Develop draft guidelines for cases where multiple functional datasets are available for a given gene, including guidance for selecting the best dataset or, where justified, combining datasets
- Support the development of tools to display multiplexed functional data to clinicians
- Develop a draft framework for ascertaining the independence of computational and functional evidence (and other types of evidence as well), and apply this framework to 5-10 well-understood, high-quality datasets.
- Development of a functional data curation team consisting of a clinician (e.g. GC, etc) and 2-3 curators who can evaluate the clinical utility of MAVE data, nominate suitable datasets for curation into MaveDB, curate all clinically relevant metadata and conduct dataset calibration
- Definition of a clinical curation data model, in partnership with the atlas effort data coordinating center and partner organizations (e.g. ClinVar, ClinGen, international equivalents)
- Delivery of a pilot curation project encompassing 10-20 genes
- Delivery of a draft clinical variant effect data discovery and use interface
- Pilot-scale federation of clinically curated data within MaveDB with partner organizations (e.g. ClinVar)
- Establish a forum with key stakeholders in the genetics diagnostics industry, including the largest providers of widely-used clinical diagnostic decision support software, to inform and influence the development of the software tools used globally.

Middle phase milestones

- Release guidelines for cases where multiple functional datasets are available for a given gene, including guidance for selecting the best dataset or, where justified, combining datasets
- Release guidelines for evaluating the quality of MAVE datasets that includes more definitive guidance on truth sets, and is updated for the SVCv4 standards
- Develop systematic process for curating truth sets from disparate data types
- Apply the framework for ascertaining computational and functional evidence independence widely
- Develop a plan for replacing largely manual gene-specific analyses of MAVE datasets with an automated, scalable procedure
- Clinical curation of functional data sets at the required pace (several hundred per year)
- Fully automated federation of data in MaveDB with ClinVar

Late phase

- Analysis of lessons learned and articulation of a plan for a complete atlas

Training a global community of clinicians and clinical scientists that can effectively use functional data

Currently, clinical labs and clinicians struggle to discover and effectively use functional data. To overcome this problem, infrastructure and training are needed. Alongside this training, tooling must be built and maintained to

share these curated data through ClinVar, the ClinGen Variant Curation Interface, and other places where clinicians and clinical labs discover evidence for variant classification. Lastly, clinicians must be trained to use the data.

Ongoing work: A foundational workshop curriculum on functional assay data for clinical variant curators and other experts has been developed and offered opportunistically in Australia and Europe. Individual workshops (e.g. at the Mutational Scanning Symposium and Curating the Clinical Genome) focused on the interface of multiplexed functional data and the clinic have taken place. But, these trainings have yet to be deployed widely.

Approximate effort required: small (e.g. 1 group with ~2-3 FTE)

Early phase milestones:

- Development of a pilot workshop on the discovery and use of functional data focused on new informatics resources such as the clinical interface in MaveDB

Middle phase milestones:

- Refinement of the workshop on the discovery and use of functional data, annual instances of the workshop in the US, Europe and elsewhere, construction of durable online resources with the same content

Late phase:

- Analysis of lessons learned and articulation of a plan for a complete atlas

Enabling development of variant-specific therapies

Currently, we do not understand how most pathogenic variants discovered so far impact molecular and cellular phenotypes, meaning that we cannot develop variant-specific therapies. The AVE community has developed a suite of MAVEs that can measure specific disease-related and druggable mechanisms of pathogenicity. Thus, if widely deployed, MAVEs could reveal the set of all variants in clinically important genes that impacted a phenotype targetable by a particular therapy. Such data could serve as the basis for models that could predict variant effects on targetable phenotypes across the genome. This information would be invaluable in selecting therapies for development, in stratifying patients for trials and in determining whether new patients would benefit from the drug. MAVE-derived variant effect data can be used to understand variant pathomechanism.

Ongoing work: The use of MAVEs to discover variant pathomechanism for the purpose of drug development or targeting is nascent. For example, corrector drugs have been designed to stabilize and improve CFTR function to treat cystic fibrosis, and a MAVE was used to discern *CFTR* variants that were ameliorated by two of these drugs. A yeast complementation MAVE identified which variants of cystathionine beta-synthase could be ameliorated with vitamin B₆ treatment. A MAVE of *MC4R*, a G-protein coupled receptor implicated in obesity, revealed variants amenable to a corrector therapy. Splice-aware MAVEs have been used to guide ASO development.

Approximate effort required: Medium (e.g. 5 groups with ~4 FTE)

Early phase milestones:

- Formation of partnerships with drug developers
- Definition of a core set of drug-targetable molecular and cellular phenotypes
 - Establishment of MAVEs specialized for each phenotype
 - Establishment of models to predict each phenotype

- Definition of a core set of genes with existing variant-specific drugs, or where variant specific drugs could be rapidly developed
 - Collection of pilot experimental and predictive data for all variants 1-3 genes

Middle phase milestones:

- Scaling of data collection and model predictions to 10-20 genes, with targets chosen in partnership with drug developers
- Evaluation and refinement of model predictions using experimental data generated in the early phase
- Use of variant effect data to guide clinical trials
- Expansion of the core set of drug-targetable molecular and cellular phenotypes

Late phase:

- Prediction of druggable molecular and cellular phenotypes for all pathogenic variants

Table 1: Estimated number of groups and FTE per activity

Category	Activity	Number of groups	FTE per group	Total FTE
Data production	Large scale	4	15	60
Data production	Medium scale	10	6	60
Technology	Cost reduction/scaling	4	3	12
Technology	Context-aware assays and models	4	5	20
Technology	Phenotype-rich assays and models	4	5	20
Coordination	Production prioritization/coordination	1	2	2
Coordination	Data coordination and dissemination	1	10	10
Coordination	Uniform data analysis	1	4	4
Coordination	Data curation and benchmarking	3	2	6
Coordination	Training researchers	1	2	2
Clinical translation	Truth sets and clinical guidance	1	8	8
Clinical translation	Training clinicians/clinician scientists	1	2	2
Clinical translation	Enabling variant-specific therapies	5	4	20
Total		40		226

Appendix I - DRAFT Goal 1 description

Goal 1: creating variant effect data and models for addressing VUS

The goal of this effort is to maximize the direct utility of invested resources by applying existing assays to genes with the highest burden of VUS and most clinical applicability. This effort would provide at least one piece of high-quality functional data and at least one high-quality prediction for as many current and future VUS as possible.

Assumptions

- Coverage of VUS will be maximized by focusing only on protein coding genes
- Sufficient VUS can be covered with existing assays, such that further technology development to capture complex variant effects (e.g. on transcriptomes, cell phenotypes, etc) is lower priority
- Current predictive models, which provide binary predictions of variant effect (e.g. loss of function vs. normal function) are sufficiently good for many genes

Principles of gene prioritization

- Pick genes with the highest density of VUS, removing some genes that are impractical because of their length or other characteristics (e.g. *TTN*)
- Pick genes based on clinical utility (e.g. impact on genomic medicine today, etc)
- Pick genes on basis of ability to demonstrate accuracy (e.g. # of control variants)
- Pick genes where VUS are enriched in individuals of non-European-like ancestry to address historic inequities in genetic medicine
- Pick genes where currently available and scalable assays will work
- Pick genes where currently available computational predictors function well, to maximize reclassification of VUS by combining functional data and predictions

Early emphasis (% allocation of resources)

- Develop innovative approaches to scale existing multiplexed assays (40%)
- Develop innovative approaches to improve the accuracy of current predictive models (20%)
- Increase gene coverage by developing novel assays that fill important gaps (5%)
- Evaluate utility and deficiencies of already scalable assays (5%)
- Organize community of small scale mapmakers with bespoke assays around VUS elimination (5%)
- Build digital infrastructure for functional data deposition, QC/QA and dissemination into clinical decision support systems, with a focus on eliminating VUS (20%)
- Revise clinical guidelines (ACMG/ClinGen, etc) in anticipation of these functional data arriving (5%)

Late emphasis (% allocation of resources)

- Large-scale generation of data using existing or minimally optimized assays, largely from a small number of functional genome centers (80%)
- Curate and calibrate functional data and predictions for clinical use (5%)
- Improve integration of functional data into clinical workflows (15%)

Appendix II - DRAFT Goal 2 description

Goal 2: building a foundational understanding of variant pathomechanism

The goal of this effort is to develop and deploy functional assays and predictive models that can generate a comprehensive understanding of how variants perturb molecular (e.g. splicing, protein activity, stability, localisation, etc) and cellular (e.g. transcriptomic, proteomic, and functional state) phenotypes. This effort would provide multiple pieces of functional data to dissect how VUS exert their effect and will enable the development of models capable of predicting mechanisms of pathogenicity. This proposal would build out a large suite of technologies and apply them to a focused set of genes, developing a comprehensive description of variant pathomechanism. With a budget of ~1M variant effect measurements, SNVs in ~200 genes could be exhaustively covered with 10 different assays.

Assumptions

- Current technologies can serve some high-need genes to produce useful information, but new methods are needed to provide mechanistic insights and also to assay most genes
- Deep mechanistic characterization of variants in a set of well-chosen genes will enable training of models that can predict the mechanism of a variant's effect
- Generating a holistic characterization of variant mechanism by applying many assays that probe different molecular and cellular functions for fewer genes will be useful clinically and also answer questions about what depth of characterization will be needed for other genes
- Understanding the molecular, cellular and genetic mode of action of variants will enable better diagnosis and also development of variant-specific therapies

Principles of gene and assay prioritization

- Pick genes where knowledge of mechanism for pathogenic variants could be most clinically impactful
- Pick genes with well understood mechanisms of molecular and cellular function that could be extended to the variant level
- Pick genes with incomplete penetrance and variable expressivity
- Pick genes and assays that measure phenotypes in which computational predictors perform poorly
- Explore non-coding variation where there is evidence it causes or modulates disease

Early emphasis (% allocation of resources)

- Develop innovative approaches to characterize variant effects on a range of molecular, cellular and tissue/developmental phenotypes (40%)
- Apply a range of mechanistically informative assays to a basis set of genes (30%)
- Explore computational models that can make mechanistic predictions (20%)
- Revise clinical guidelines to move from “functional vs. non-functional” to incorporate mechanistic insights (10%)

Late emphasis (% allocation of resources)

- Large-scale data generation using newly developed and existing assays, with the goal of exhaustive mechanistic characterization (50%)
- Develop foundation models for mechanistic variant effect predictions (20%)
- Develop a new, “variant pathomechanism” data resource that enables deposition, dissemination, discovery and exploration of mechanistic variant effect information (10%)
- Improve integration of mechanistic functional data into clinical workflows (10%)

- Develop variant-informed or variant-specific therapies (10%)

Appendix III - DRAFT Disease, gene and variant prioritization

Prioritizing targets for MAVE studies should ideally depend on several factors, including a) clinical need (the VUS problem, both current and anticipated, and considering frequency of VUS in non-European populations as well as availability of therapeutic interventions and/or clinical trials); b) availability of assays that are (individually or collectively) likely to reflect the pathobiology of variants; c) the cost of carrying out the assay(s), which depends both on the nature of the assays and the length of the protein or genomic element; d) the willingness of appropriate experts in the biological and clinical aspects of the assay to engage; and e) ability to validate the functional assay data once it exists.

Prioritization should consider focusing on evaluating sets of genes in a gene pathway that all contribute to a common disease, to better scale pathomechanism assessment. Examples include muscular dystrophies, RASopathies, cardiac sarcomere disorders, or channelopathies.